

Wind lidar – then and now and back again? A personal perspective

IEA Wind Task 52

Kassel – September 2025

Motivation of this presentation

- I was reading a 2025 PV report last week.....
- Interesting industry engagement (!)
- Recent project calls
- Are we in danger of taking a step backwards?

accurate and acceptable level for the wind speeds observed during the verification. [redacted] considers that the [redacted] [redacted] device under test can be used for formal wind resource assessments. Specifically, [redacted] concludes that this lidar may be employed as a standalone measurement system – replacing a conventional met mast – given the following criteria are met:

- (1) The lidar is deployed on an offshore platform or in relatively simple terrain.
- (2) In addition, it is considered good practice to ensure the long-term stability of the device through correlations with on-site masts or through the use of a post deployment performance verification campaign.

After 23 years+ of lidar measurements are we really still here?

Where I started.....

- I love sodar
- Started use around 2001/2002
- AQ500 – unit 3
- Note the asymmetric design !
- How to prove it worked to wind industry requirements?
- Start of a **long** conversation about testing with Andrew Tindal at Garrad Hassan
- Allowed the use of sodar onshore with a metmast or after a metmast test
- Which raised the question - How do we test?

Building up evidence

- Initial QA documents dated back to 1994
- Looked at
 - linear correlations
 - bias
 - NOT TI – but σ_w and σ_θ
 - Was not interested in data completion
 - Was interested in atmospheric conditions

A Look Back on Two Decades of Doppler Sodar Comparison Studies

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ABSTRACT

This paper is a compilation of the results obtained from various Doppler sodar comparison experiments conducted over the last 20 years. These studies have attempted to quantify the uncertainties in sodar-derived values of the horizontal wind speed, wind direction, standard deviation of the vertical wind speed σ_w , and standard horizontal wind direction σ_θ . Doppler sodar configurations examined in these studies included bi-static and phased arrays. In most cases, reference measurements used for comparison were made by a sensors. Many investigators have used simple linear regressions and other statistical measures such as coefficient, bias (mean difference), comparability (root-mean-square difference), and precision (precision) in an attempt to quantify these errors. The sodar-derived wind speed and wind direction are highly correlated with reference measurements ($r = 0.92$) with a precision of 1.06 m s^{-1} and 21.5° , respectively, for wind speed. Correlations of sodar-derived values of σ_w were not quite as good ($r = 0.81$) with an average precision of 0.57 . Past studies have shown that σ_w accuracies vary significantly from day (convective conditions) to day (stratiform conditions). Very few data values were available for σ_θ , which had a poor correlation of 0.57 and a precision of 1.06 . The conclusions from many of these studies have shown that Doppler sodars can accurately observe wind speed and wind direction. Values of σ_w have larger uncertainties, while estimates of σ_θ have errors that are unacceptable for any practical use. Much of the observed scatter in sodar wind measurement is a number of factors. These include, but are not limited to, instrument configuration, spatio-temporal noise, and processing techniques.

17 - 1996

DEVELOPMENT OF EPA QUALITY ASSURANCE AND QUALITY CONTROL GUIDANCE FOR GROUND-BASED REMOTE SENSORS FOR USE IN REGULATORY MONITORING

by

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Ninth Joint Conference on the Applications of Air Pollution Meteorology
with the Air and Waste Management Association

American Meteorological Society

January 28 - February 2, 1996
Atlanta, Georgia

Beatrice & Fino

2003/4:

- EU –WISE project and PIE (2004)
- EU DOWNViND project (2003)
 - Question, can a lidar replace a met mast?
 - ZX lidar no 6!
- So, I wrote a protocol.....

Implemented and published by Windtest k-w-k and Detlef Stein (nee Kindler)

- 3 month onshore
- 5 months offshore

Kindler et al *Meteorologische Zeitschrift*, Vol. 16, No. 5, 479-489
(October 2007) (published online 2007)

Fino test

- Fino test was the winner
- 8 months
- Zero reliability (the platform got damaged in a storm)
- Mainly concerned with linear correlations
- Based on an old sodar paper – started looking at atmospheric conditions
- Data availability started to creep in
- Already observing differences between onshore and offshore testing
- We also looked at Ti.....

At this point we take a step back – Why lidar?

At this point we take a step back – Why lidar?

Norsewind – the call & the solution

- 7 million Euro Contribution
- 12 Million Euro Project
- Use physical data offshore
- Integration of datasets
- Reduce Uncertainty (?)
- Data early in the project cycle
- Better data, better informed

R&D Priorities regarding Wind Resource Estimation and Mapping

Maximum availability of wind resource data, if possible in the public domain, to ensure that financiers, insurers and project developers can develop high quality projects as efficiently as possible, and avoid project failure through inaccurate data

Resource mapping of areas with a high probability of high wind resource potential, but as yet unexplored, including the Baltic, North and Black Seas.

Development of cost effective measuring units, including communications and processing, and which are easily transportable, for the assessment of wind resource characteristics, such as LIDAR, SODAR and satellite observation.

The test

To enable lidar we needed:

- Systematic testing protocol
- How to do it?
 - Use a tall mast
 - Use a well-established test site (conditions well understood)
 - System had undergone long term testing there
 - Can then enable short term testing as long term characteristics well understood

The test

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Type qualification

Unit qualification

The original NORSEWIND KPIs

- Committee numbers
- Data completion was a minimum of 10 days of testing
- Linear regression targets
- These may look familiar
- However, no uncertainty so no bin completion and no formal value proposition

Parameter	Criteria	Sub-Ranges (height & speed)
Absolute error	<0.5m/s; Not more than 10% of data to exceed this value	All valid data
Data Availability	Assessed case by case – Environmental conditions dependent	All valid data
Linear Regression - Slope	Between 0.98 and 1.01 <0.015 variation in slope	All heights 4-8m/s & 8-12 m/s
Linear Regression – R ²	>0.98	All heights 4-8m/s & 8-12m/s

Start of uncertainty quantification

- Articles such as these started to appear
- Starting to tackle lidar uncertainty
- 1st steps to contextualise within the framework standards – (power curve)

WIND ENERGY
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SPECIAL ISSUE PAPER

Lidar profilers in the context of wind energy—a verification procedure for traceable measurements

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Risø DTU
National Laboratory
for Sustainable Energy

Calibrating nacelle lidars

DTU Wind Energy E-0020

Michael Courtney

UpWind
D1. Uncertainties in wind
assessment with LIDAR

TCT KPIs

- Applied formal stage/type framework to FLS
- Introduced bin completion
- Discussed uncertainty but no firm proposal
- Introduced measurement performance KPIs
- Tries to normalise analysis approach

KPI	Definition / rationale	Acceptance Criteria
		Minimum requirement
X_{mws}	<p>Mean Wind Speed – slope</p> <p>Slope returned from single variant regression with the regression analysis constrained to pass through the origin.</p> <p>Slope for unconstrained 2-parameter linear regression.</p> <p>A tolerance is imposed on the slope value.</p> <p>Analysis shall be applied to wind speed ranges:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4 to 16 m/s. All above 2 m/s. <p>given achieved data coverage requirements.</p>	0.98 – 1.02
R^2_{mws}	<p>Mean Wind Speed – coefficient of determination</p> <p>Correlation coefficient returned from single variant and multi-regression</p> <p>A tolerance is imposed on the correlation coefficient value.</p> <p>Analysis shall be applied to wind speed ranges:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4 to 16 m/s. All above 2 m/s. <p>given achieved data coverage requirements.</p>	> 0.98
OFF_{mws}	<p>Mean Wind Speed – offset</p> <p>In terms of the calculated offset when undertaking a two-parameter linear regression analysis.</p>	+/- 0.2 m/s

The Carbon Trust Offshore Wind Accelerator roadmap for the commercial acceptance of floating LiDAR technology

Version 3.0 | June 2025

TI_{MBE}	<p>Mean Bias Error</p> <p>The mean of the difference between the recorded TI_{FLS} and TI_{REF} shall be evaluated for both all-data and wind speed binned (0.5m/s bin widths) data.</p> <p>For all data and for each wind speed bin, calculate the Mean Bias Error as follows:</p> $TI_{MBE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{l=1}^n TI_{FLS_l} - TI_{REF_l}$ <p>the mean of all TI differences, used to assess the accuracy of the measurement.</p> <p>Mean bias error is expressed as an absolute % error in TI.</p>
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50-X

- Formalises the used of lidars into a normative standard
- IEA Wind task 52 is helping to inform some of the recommendations
- Key to 50-X is the uncertainty framework
- Remember - Uncertainty justifies measurement campaigns

Some current Barriers

- data availability KPIs
 - A carrot & stick approach
- How does lidar work?
- TI! – 20 years!
- Excellent concepts in standards not fully test driven
 - EOC & EVs
 - Uncertainty in short form testing
 - Sensitivity in short form testing

In danger of going back in time

Suggested takeaways from this ramble

- Q: is lidar able to measure everything relevant to wind energy?
 - Start looking at integrated solutions – lidar + MWR + model? – workflow development + robust verification protocols
- There are some fundamental questions requiring to be addressed to (re) enable market confidence
 - normalise IEC terminology and homogenise concepts
 - Need to fully integrate calibration testing
- We need large open data infrastructure comparison campaigns (and please don't forget me!)

Up and coming

- DSL and FLS – uncertainty quantification (needs alignment)
- SL – the case for a SL roadmap?
- Novel applications:
 - Wind lidars for boundary layer detection + wind resource (e.g. NEMO – F.IWES)
- RVO: Will launch a MWR programme looking at MWR on a floating platform
- Would it not be wonderful to integrate these two technologies:
 - Wind condition, wind resource, boundary layer height, boundary layer stability.....from one integrated device - now we have to prove it

A measurement campaign

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